

Kinetics of Resin-Catalyzed Hydrolysis of Mixtures of Esters

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Manuscript received 5 July 1979, accepted 28 January 1981

The kinetics of the catalyzed hydrolysis of binary mixtures of ethyl acetate/polyvinyl acetate, *n*-butyl acetate/isobutyl acetate and *n*-propyl acetate/*n*-butyl acetate was studied in presence of Wofatit KPS resin. In the first mixture polyvinyl acetate was excluded by sieve action, the reaction was first order with respect to ethyl acetate. A preference for the straight-chain over the branched-chain molecule was observed in the second mixture. The reaction was zero order for both esters in the mixture. In the third mixture the resin hydrolyzed both esters with comparable rates, both the rates affected one another. In the latter case the mechanism changed during the same reaction, the order was zero with respect to the ester whose hydrolysis reaction was the rate-determining step.

ION-exchange resins are used as catalysts for many chemical reactions, e.g., ester hydrolysis¹. Ion exchangers can discriminate between large and small molecules. Small molecules have free access to the interior of the resin where the catalytically active counter ions are located, while large molecules are excluded by sieve action^{2,3}. For example, the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate and polyvinyl acetate after 10 hours with Amberlite IR-120 in the hydrogen form and of particle diameter 0.5-1.0 mm, was 100% and 15.43% respectively⁴. Similarly, Linde Molecular Sieves Type 5A, which sorb straight-chain molecules but exclude branched-chain ones, catalyze dehydration of *n*-butanol without significantly affecting isobutanol⁵. Accumulation in the resin of one reactant by preferential sorption may also favour a given reaction².

The present investigation is aimed at a study of the kinetics of catalyzed hydrolysis of some pairs of esters in presence of strong-acidic cation-exchange resin in the hydrogen form. It is also the intention to go more deeper in the mathematical treatment of the kinetics of the simplest model concerning a first-order irreversible catalyzed hydrolysis reaction.

Experimental

The cation-exchanger catalyst :

Wofatit KPS (2 and 16% DVB) resin in the hydrogen form was used as a cation-exchanger catalyst. The resin has been described previously⁶. It had an average particle diameter of 0.06 mm. Its total scientific weight capacity was determined statically and decreased with increasing resin crosslinkage⁷. It was 4.93 and 4.23 meq/g dry resin at resin crosslinkage of 2 and 16% DVB respectively.

The ester solutions :

Three pairs of esters namely ethyl acetate/polyvinyl acetate, *n*-butyl acetate/isobutyl acetate and

n-propyl acetate/*n*-butyl acetate were used. Polyvinyl acetate was prepared as 8% w/w solution in benzene. In every mixture 2.0 ml of each ester were used. Each mixture constituted a two-phase system with water. All esters were of A.R. grade.

The catalysis operation :

The kinetic experiments for the determination of the reaction rates were carried out in aqueous solution at 42, 50, 55 and 59° with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ as mentioned previously^{8,9}.

Results and Discussion

First-order rate constants, k_1 (per g of resin) (Table 1) for the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in its mixture with 2 and 16% DVB of the resin were obtained from the graphical representation of this linear relationship⁸ :

$$\log \frac{T_\infty - T_t}{T_\infty - T_0} = \frac{k_1 w}{2.303} t \quad \dots (1)$$

where w is the weight of dry resin, t the time, T_t the titre at time t , and T_∞ that corresponding to total hydrolysis of the sample withdrawn.

The values of k_1 were exactly equal to those obtained when ethyl acetate was hydrolyzed alone under the same working conditions⁹. This means that the polyvinyl acetate was completely excluded from the resin by the sieve action due to its large molecule^{2,4}.

The zero-order rate constants, k_0 (per g of resin) (Table 1) were obtained for the hydrolysis of the mixtures *n*-butyl acetate/isobutyl acetate and *n*-propyl acetate/*n*-butyl acetate from the graphical representation of this expression⁸ :

$$\text{moles hydrolyzed}/l = k_0 w t \quad \dots (2)$$

TABLE 1—THE RATE CONSTANTS (PER G OF RESIN) AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF HETEROGENEOUS CATALYZED HYDROLYSIS OF MIXTURES OF ESTERS

System	Catalyst (Wofatit KPS)	Rate constant $\times 10^6$				Dimension	E (K cal/mole)	ΔS° (cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹)
		42°	50°	55°	59°			
Ethyl acetate/ polyvinyl acetate mixture	2% DVB	5.79	11.95	16.81	19.49	sec ⁻¹	16.5	-27.7
	16% DVB	4.46	8.51	11.08	15.88	sec ⁻¹	15.5	-31.1
<i>n</i> -butyl acetate/ isobutyl acetate mixture	2% DVB							
	1st line	0.61	0.98	1.40	1.72	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	12.6	-44.4
	2nd line	0.58	0.81	1.38	1.55	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	13.0	-48.5
	16% DVB							
	1st line	0.86	0.64	0.97	1.27	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	15.4	-36.7
	2nd line	0.82	0.56	0.96	1.18	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	15.4	-36.7
<i>n</i> -propyl acetate ^o	2% DVB	1.44	2.66	3.50	4.27	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	14.0	-88.2
	16% DVB	1.02	1.81	2.37	3.80	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	14.3	-37.9
<i>n</i> -propyl acetate/ <i>n</i> -butyl acetate mixture	2% DVB							
	1st line	1.02	1.65	2.50	2.90	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	12.8	-38.0
	2nd line	0.50	0.96	1.48	1.88	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	16.1	-34.0
	16% DVB							
	1st line	0.68	1.06	1.50	1.96	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	13.7	-41.0
	2nd line	0.47	0.79	1.14	1.48	mole l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	18.4	-48.0

For the hydrolysis of the mixture *n*-butyl acetate/isobutyl acetate in presence of 2% DVB of the resin each graph in Fig. 1 consisted of two lines of different slopes. From the slope of the first line which started from the origin (solid line) the value of k_0 was calculated (Table 1). This value of k_0 was

Fig. 1. Representation of the zero-order rate equation for the heterogeneous catalytic hydrolysis of the mixture *n*-butyl acetate/isobutyl acetate in presence of 2.0 g Wofatit KPS (2% DVB) resin in the hydrogen form at various temperatures. ○ : at 42°, × : at 50°, □ : at 55° and Δ : at 59°.

equal to that obtained for the heterogeneous hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate alone⁹. The value of k_0 for the second line (dashed line), which began after the complete hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate, was equal to that of the heterogeneous hydrolysis of isobutyl acetate⁹. The same criterion was found with 16% DVB of the resin. This means that there was no interference between both esters during the hydrolysis process. This is because the sorption of the straight-chain molecules (*n*-butyl acetate) was preferred by the resin than that of the branched-chain ones (isobutyl acetate).

As in the case of the previous system (*n*-butyl acetate/isobutyl acetate) the hydrolysis of the mixture *n*-propyl acetate/*n*-butyl acetate in presence of 2% DVB of the resin lead to graphs each of which comprised of two lines of different slopes. The values of the rate constant (Table 1) for the hydrolysis of both *n*-propyl acetate and *n*-butyl acetate were obtained from the slope of the first line which started from the origin. These values of k_0 (Table 1) were always smaller than those obtained for the hydrolysis of *n*-propyl acetate when the latter was hydrolyzed alone (Table 1). This is because the rate constant of the hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate was smaller than that of *n*-propyl acetate, the presence of the former affected the rate constant of the latter. Similarly, the second part of each graph gave the value of the rate constant for the hydrolysis of both esters. Its value was greater than that obtained for the hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate (except that at 42° and 2% DVB which lies in the range of the experimental error) when the latter was hydrolyzed alone. This is because the presence of *n*-propyl acetate accelerated the rate of hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate. The same criterion was found with 16% DVB of the resin.

On the other hand for the mixture *n*-propyl acetate/*n*-butyl acetate the influence of the hydrolysis of one of these esters into the hydrolysis

process of the other was studied. From the values of k_0 of the hydrolysis of esters in the latter mixture (Table 1) as well as those⁹ from the hydrolysis of each ester alone, the % decrease in the rate of hydrolysis of *n*-propyl acetate was calculated with 2 and 16% DVB of the resin (Table 2). This represents its % hydrolysis in presence of *n*-butyl acetate. Similarly, the % increase in the rate of hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate was calculated in presence of *n*-propyl acetate (Table 2). From this table it is clear that with a resin of 16% DVB the % decrease in the rate of hydrolysis of *n*-propyl acetate as well as the % increase in the rate of hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate was greater than that with a resin of 2%

TABLE 2—THE EFFECT OF INTERFERENCE OF THE RATE OF HYDROLYSIS OF ONE ESTER ON THAT OF THE OTHER IN THE MIXTURE *n*-PROPYL ACETATE/*n*-BUTYL ACETATE

t°C	Catalyst			
	KPS, 2% DVB		KPS, 16% DVB	
	1st line % decrease in the rate of <i>n</i> - propyl acetate	2nd line % increase in the rate of <i>n</i> - butyl acetate	1st line % decrease in the rate of <i>n</i> - propyl acetate	2nd line % increase in the rate of <i>n</i> - butyl acetate
42	29.2	—	38.1	29.7
50	38.0	3.2	41.7	24.7
55	28.6	2.1	36.7	17.6
59	32.1	9.5	40.6	12.6

DVB. This can be attributed to the sorption of *n*-propyl acetate which is greater with a resin of 2% DVB than that with a resin of 16% DVB. Accordingly the greater the % decrease in the rate of hydrolysis of *n*-propyl acetate the greater would be the % increase in the rate of hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate.

It is useful to provide a quantitative treatment of the hydrolysis of all mixtures under investigation in terms of the values of the activation parameters, E , ΔH^* , ΔG^* and ΔS^* . The activation energy, E , is calculated from Arrhenius plot. The change of enthalpy of activation, ΔH^* is deduced from this relation¹⁰ :

$$\Delta H^* = E - RT \quad \dots (3)$$

The change of free energy of activation, ΔG^* , is evaluated from Eyring's equation¹⁰ :

$$K = \frac{kT}{h} e^{-\Delta G^*/RT} \quad \dots (4)$$

where K is the rate constant, k Boltzman constant and h is Planck's constant. The change of entropy of activation is estimated from this relation :

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^* \quad \dots (5)$$

The value of ΔG^* was between 25 and 27 K cal/mole and was independent of the resin structure as

well as the molecular weight of the ester. So, ΔH^* changes in accordance with the variation of ΔS^* .

From the values of E (Table 1), it is clear that the hydrolysis of all binary mixtures under investigation was controlled by the chemical reaction in the interior of the resin particles. This means that sorption equilibrium of the reacting species between the resin and the solution is rapidly established and is maintained throughout the process. Slow intraparticle diffusion may reduce the over-all rate, especially if the reactant molecules are large and thus have a low mobility in the resin catalyst^{9,11}. This can be observed by comparing the values of E (Table 1) with 2% DVB of the resin for the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in its mixture (16.5 K cal/mole) and that for the hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate or iso-butyl acetate (13.0 K cal/mole) in its mixture.

The values of ΔS^* were similar to those established by other workers for the heterogeneous hydrolysis of esters^{9,12}. The ester molecule suffers a loss of some internal degree of freedom during the process of the formation of the activated complex. Ester molecules with many internal degrees of freedom have more entropy to lose. For these, ΔS^* becomes negative.

For the hydrolysis of the mixture *n*-propyl acetate/*n*-butyl acetate with the resin of 2% DVB the value of E for the first line was equal to that for the hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate alone (Table 1). This means that the rate-determining step was the internal chemical reaction of *n*-butyl acetate in the resin and its order (zero order) is imposed on the over-all reaction. The value of E for the second line with the resin of 2% DVB was higher than that for the hydrolysis of *n*-propyl acetate alone (Table 1). This is attributed to the slower rate of hydrolysis of *n*-butyl acetate (Table 1). The situation was reversed with respect to the rate-determining step and the order of *n*-propyl acetate is imposed on the over-all reaction. The same criterion was found with the resin of 16% DVB. With the latter the effect of intraparticle diffusion on the rate-determining step was more pronounced than that with the resin of 2% DVB especially with a large molecule like *n*-butyl acetate. This emphasized the equal values of E in both parts of the graphs. This means that the apparent activation energy was a crossbreed between those of diffusion (6-10 Kcal/mole)^{7,13} and of the chemical reaction (10-20 K cal/mole)¹⁴. An evidence for this is the effect of temperature on the % increase in the rate of *n*-butyl acetate where there exists a reverse relationship between them (Table 2). This can be attributed to the dependence of the sorption of ester molecules on temperature since the potential rate-determining step of the sorption under the present working conditions was the particle diffusion¹⁵. A rise in temperature speeds up the chemical reaction more than the diffusion processes because the activation energy

of the former is considerably higher than that of the latter. High temperature thus favours intraparticle diffusion limitation. Since the latter can never be the sole rate-determining step¹⁶, thus the reaction with the resin of 16% DVB is controlled by a combination of intraparticle chemical reaction and intraparticle diffusion.

It is noteworthy to go more deeper in the mathematics of the internal reaction control as the rate-determining step and to elucidate the effect of intraparticle diffusion on the latter. It was reasonable to choose the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in its mixture to serve as an example of a first-order irreversible reaction. This is because the mathematics of intraparticle diffusion-limited reactions of other than first-order are rather complex¹⁷.

For internal reaction control the half-time (Table 3) of the first-order irreversible hydrolysis reaction of ethyl acetate is given by the following expression¹⁸ :

$$t_{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.69 \frac{V + \lambda \bar{V}}{K \lambda \bar{V}} \quad \dots (6)$$

where \bar{V} and V are the total volume of the catalyst (equal to 2.7 cm³ with 2% DVB and 1.86 cm³ with 16% DVB) and that of the solution (2 ml of ethyl acetate) respectively. The distribution coefficient, λ (Table 3) of the ester between resin (in the Na⁺ form to avoid catalytic reaction)^{19,20} and solution was dependent on the degree of resin crosslinkage as well as on the temperature. From the values of $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Table 3) it is clear that the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate with 2% DVB was faster than that with 16% DVB.

When intraparticle diffusion is taken into consideration as a factor affecting the rate-determining step, $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ is accordingly larger by the factor²¹ $1/\eta$, i.e.,

$$t_{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.69 \frac{V + \lambda \bar{V}}{K \lambda \bar{V} \eta} \quad \dots (7)$$

The degree of catalyst utilization²¹, ω , is a function of the Thiele modulus²¹ :

$$\omega = r \left(\frac{k}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (8)$$

The greater the value of, η , the smaller is the value of, ω . The latter was derived for reactant penetration into pores for spherical geometry²¹, D is the intraparticle diffusion coefficient. A solution for the η (ω) function is given by Helfferich²².

For internal reaction control $\omega < 0.5$, and for strong diffusion limitation $\omega > 15$ ²¹. To examine the internal reaction control, put $\omega = 0.4$. From the

Table²² of the function η (ω), $\eta = 0.9895$. When this value of, η , is introduced into equation (7) the values of $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ were almost equal to those found in Table 3. The smaller the value of, ω , the greater is the value of, η , and the smaller should be the deviation from the values of $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ in Table 3.

TABLE 3—THE VALUES OF $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ AND λ FOR THE HETEROGENEOUS HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL ACETATE IN ITS MIXTURE

Catalyst (Wofatit KI S)	42°		50°		55°		59°	
	λ (-)	$t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (hr)	λ (-)	$t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (hr)	λ (-)	$t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (hr)	λ (-)	$t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (hr)
2% DVB	1.28	5.2	1.21	2.6	1.15	1.9	1.05	1.7
16% DVB	1.08	8.5	1.02	4.6	0.81	4.0	0.81	2.8

On the other hand to study the diffusion reaction control we should assume that $\omega = 15.1$ and accordingly²² $\eta = 0.1425$. This value of, η , when introduced into equation (7) the corresponding values of $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ should be much more greater than those found in Table 3, e.g., $t_{\frac{1}{2}} = 36.7$ hr at 42° and 2% DVB.

From the above treatment we can conclude that, ω , must be less than 0.5, and the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate is controlled by internal chemical reaction.

It was possible to calculate the diffusion coefficient, (equation 8) of ethyl acetate inside the resin particles where $\omega = 0.4$. The value of D ranged between 3.3×10^{-9} and 1.1×10^{-8} cm²/sec with 2% DVB and between 2.5×10^{-9} and 8.9×10^{-9} cm²/sec with 16% DVB of the resin at the temperature range 42-59°. These values of D should not be considered as the actual values of intraparticle diffusion coefficients of the ester molecule within the resin because they are influenced by the chemical reaction of ester hydrolysis.

The distribution coefficient and the diffusion coefficient of polyvinyl acetate must be equal to zero because it was completely excluded from the resin particles. This result may seem to be a consequence of the assumption that all counter ions are within the resin. This is not strictly true since the particles are surrounded by a counter-ion cloud²³. The reaction may occur in this cloud and also at the interface itself where fixed ionic groups are freely exposed to the solution. This means that both surface reaction control and film diffusion control were absent, and polyvinyl acetate molecules were excluded from the resin due to sieve action.

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